

Design and Development of Jute Sprouting Bag

S. D. Asagekar*, Pooja Katkar, Vaishnavi Jumade, Kiran Bhakare , Siva Tarun Noone & Shubhangi More

DKTES's Textile and Engineering Institute, Ichalkaranji

Abstract:

Sprouting is the process of germinating seeds or spores. Traditionally, cotton fabric is used to sprout cereals and pulses. This method has drawbacks; sprouts grown can spoil easily which develops an unpleasant odor. On the other hand, plastic containers, which are available in the market, may release microplastics that pose risks to both the environment and human health.

Considering these limitations, bags of Jute fabrics with three different combinations, namely untreated, scoured and bleached jute fabrics have been developed for sprouting. The efficiency of sprouting was measured in terms of length of the sprouts. The results were compared with commercially available hemp sprout bag. The length of sprouts shoots was found to be significantly higher in the jute fiber sandwiched double layer scoured and bleached jute bag.

Keywords: *Hemp, Jute, Sandwiched, Sprouting Bags*

1. Introduction

Sprouting is the natural process through which seeds or spores germinate, leading to the growth of young plants. Sprouts can be cultivated both commercially and at home, making them a versatile addition to any diet. They are particularly valued in raw food diets for their nutritional richness. Sprouts are an excellent source of easily digestible energy, vitamins, minerals, amino acids, and proteins. These nutrients are also vital for human health, contributing to various benefits such as blood sugar regulation, improved digestion, and a reduced risk of heart disease.

Sprouts can be cultivated using various methods, such as the traditional approach using a cotton cloth or the modern method using plastic containers. However, both methods have their own drawbacks. With the cotton cloth method, sprouts take longer to grow and are prone to fungal contamination over time, leading to unpleasant odours. On the other hand, plastic containers release micro-plastics, which are harmful to both consumers and the environment. To address these issues, jute sprouting bags have been designed and developed as a sustainable alternative. These bags offer an eco-friendly solution that overcomes the limitations of traditional methods, providing a healthier and more environmentally conscious alternative for growing sprouts.

2. Material

Jute Fabric, Jute Fibre, Hemp Sprouting Bags

3. Methodology

3.1 Development of Sprouting Bags

Jute fabric of specification 200 GSM was procured from the market. For enhancing the absorbency and moisture retaining characteristics of jute fabric, scouring and bleaching of jute fabric was carried out. The sprouting bags were stitched using untreated and treated jute fabrics, with following specifications;

- i. Single layer jute sprouting bag
- ii. Double layer jute sprouting bag
- iii. Fibre sandwiched jute sprouting bag (two layer of jute fabrics and in between jute fibre is placed with vertical orientation)

In all, six sprouting bags were stitched with following combinations,

Figure 1 - Jute Fabric Sprout Bag

Table 1 - Sprout Bag Particulars

Sr. No.	Type of Jute Fabric	Specification
1	Untreated Fabric	Single layer
2	Untreated Fabric	Double layer
3	Untreated Fabric	Fibre sandwiched jute sprouting bag
4	Scoured and Bleached Fabric	Single layer
5	Scoured and Bleached Fabric	Double layer
6	Scoured and Bleached Fabric	Fibre sandwiched jute sprouting bag

3.2 Characteristics of Jute Fabric

The jute fabric characteristics were measured by referring various ASTM standards. Following table indicate test results of jute fabric.

Table 2 - Properties of Jute Fabric

Fabric	Jute (200 GSM)
Warp Way Strip strength	40 KGF
Weft way Strip Strength	26 KGF
Air Permeability	1.78 cm ³ /cm ² /sec
Porosity	0.23 μm ²
Thickness	0.88 mm
Moisture Regain	12%
Weave	Plain Weave
EPI	15
PPI	12

The performance of bags was checked by taking, mung bean seeds which were kept in water for soaking for 12 hours, which are then used for the sprouting. The bags were filled with same weight of soaked bean seeds. In first part of study, these bags were kept in incubator. The temperature is an important factor for sprouting and the growth of the sprouts. Hence, the study was conducted at different incubator temperature, viz. 10 °C, 20 °C, 30 °C. The efficiency of sprouting was measured in terms of length of sprouts. The length of sprouts was measured after 8 hrs and 24 hrs. The same procedure is repeated by using the treated jute bags, untreated jute bags and commercially available Hemp sprout bag for sprouting, at room temperature.

4. Results and Discussion

It is observed that for incubator period of 8 hrs and 24 hrs there is no significant difference in sprouting length between single layer and double layer fabric bag. However, for the sandwiched layer bag the sprout length is significantly higher, than both single and double layer bags. This may be due to the more retention of moisture in additional fibre layer between the two layers of fabric.

Table 3 - Effect of incubation temperature and time

Particulars of bag	Temperature of Incubator	Sprout Length (8 Hrs) in mm	Sprout Length (24 Hrs) in mm
Single Layer Jute	10	1	2.5
Single Layer Jute	20	3.5	4.5
Single Layer Jute	30	3.5	4.5
Double Layer Jute	10	1.5	3
Double Layer Jute	20	3	4.5
Double Layer Jute	30	4	5
Double Layer Jute –Fibre Sandwiched	10	2	3.5
Double Layer Jute –Fibre Sandwiched	20	4.5	6
Double Layer Jute –Fibre Sandwiched	30	4.5	6.5

To simulate actual sprouting, the experiment was conducted at room temperature, in the atmosphere for observing the sprouting performance of these bags in fields. The table.4 indicates the results of length of sprouts at room temperature.

Table 4 - Sprout length at room temperature in the atmosphere

Particulars of bag	Treatments	Sprout Length (8 Hrs) in mm	Sprout Length (24 Hrs) in mm
Single Layer Jute	Untreated	5	10
Single Layer Jute	Scoured and bleached	6.5	15
Double Layer Jute	Untreated	9	27
Double Layer Jute	Scoured and bleached	10	28
Double Layer Jute –Fibre Sandwiched	Untreated	10.5	29
Double Layer Jute – Fibre Sandwiched	Scoured and bleached	11.5	30
Commercially available Hemp Fabric Sprout bag	Purchased from Market	6	12

- The scoured and bleached fabric bags shows significantly higher sprout lengths in comparison with untreated bags, for both 8 hrs and 24 hrs exposure period. This may be attributed to the increased water absorbency on removal of oils and fats of scoured and bleached fabric.
- It is also observed that the sprout length for jute fibres sandwiched scoured and bleached double layer fabric is higher for given period of time, this may be due to the generation of healthy climate between the two layers of bag, which favours the germination process.
- Further, the length of sprouts is more in case of the jute fibres sandwiched scoured and bleached double layer fabric in comparison with commercially available hemp sprout bag. This may be related to the special design of double layered sandwich bags.

5. Conclusion

The length of the sprouts in jute bag is longer even for short span of sprouting time. The scoured and bleached, double layer jute bag, sandwiched with jute fiber shows significantly higher sprout length viz.30 mm at room temperature, when kept for 24 hrs, while hemp bag shows only 12 mm length. The sandwiched double layer scoured and bleached jute bag has been proved superior in comparison with commercially available hemp sprout bags. In this era, where time, sustainability and environmental awareness is valuable, jute sprouting bags can be economical and sustainable solution for sprouting the cereals and pulses

References:

- [1] Rony Mia et al, Woolenization of jute fibre, European Scientific Journal 13(30), October 2017
- [2] Handbook of Textile Fibres, James Gordon Cook
- [3] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sprouting>
- [4] <https://sproutman.com/pages/sprouting>